

Promoting Algorithmic Thinking: Students Using mBots and Block-Based Programming

Practical Insights into Two Different Problem-Based Approaches

Frauke Ritter, Anette Bentz and Bernhard Standl

Karlsruhe University of Education, Bismarckstr. 10, 76133 Karlsruhe, Germany

Abstract

In our Teaching-Learning-Laboratory for Informatics (TLL), students from the Karlsruhe University of Education develop workshops and try them out on school classes. The workshops aim to teach the pupils algorithmic thinking - here mBot-Robots are used, which are programmed with a block-based programming language in 4 modules (disco animation, rescue scenario, Formula 1 - race and maze). Methodologically, two different problem-based approaches are evaluated: a guided problem-oriented approach, which didactically follows a semantic wave, and a constructivist problem-based approach. We will test both approaches in the workshop and then discuss them.

Keywords

Algorithmic Thinking, block-based programming, Robotics, Semantic Wave

Description of the Workshop

In our digitized world, it is important that students learn the core competency of computational thinking at school in a sustainable way in order to understand the technologies and processes behind the tools and end devices they use every day. This is achieved on the one hand with the help of motivating tasks or gadgets (computational action [1]) and on the other hand with the help of suitable didactic approaches that go beyond a mere programming course. To promote school students' algorithmic thinking competencies, we elaborated two teaching approaches: a guided problem-based [2, 3] and a constructionist problem-based one [4, 5]. In this workshop, we will show how we implement these two approaches with mBots in workshops at our computer science teaching-learning lab. The workshop will also provide the opportunity to experiment directly with the mBot robots. mBot robots are easy-to-build robots with light and ultrasonic sensors as input options and an LED display as a further output option in addition to driving the robot itself. This simple handling with basic robot functions and the option of block-based

Informatics in Schools. A step beyond digital education. 15th International Conference on Informatics in Schools: Situation, Evolution, and Perspectives, ISSEP 2022, Vienna, Austria, September 26–28, 2022

✉ frauke.ritter@ph-karlsruhe.de (F. Ritter); anette.bentz@ph-karlsruhe.de (A. Bentz); bernhard.standl@ph-karlsruhe.de (B. Standl)

🌐 <https://www.ph-karlsruhe.de> (F. Ritter); <https://www.ph-karlsruhe.de> (A. Bentz); <https://www.ph-karlsruhe.de> (B. Standl)

🆔 0000-0001-5744-9456 (F. Ritter); 0000-0002-8849-2980 (B. Standl)

© 2022 Copyright for this paper by its authors. Use permitted under Creative Commons License Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0).

programming using the software mBlock make the mBot robot a motivating gadget for students. Therefore, the aim of the workshop is to get to know, carry out and discuss the two different teaching approaches (a guided problem-based and a constructionist problem-based) in one workshop with the same content (see Figure 1): first a disco animation is programmed, then a rescue scenario in a crisis area, a Formula 1 race and finally a labyrinth. After trying both approaches, the advantages and disadvantages of each will be discussed in order to further develop our concepts.

Figure 1: mBot workshop with two didactical approaches in comparison: SWAT concept using a semantic wave and a constructionist problem-based concept.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the Vector Foundation.

References

- [1] M. Tissenbaum, J. Sheldon, H. Abelson, Viewpoint from computational thinking to computational action, *Communications of the ACM* 62 (2019) 34–36. doi:10.1145/3265747.
- [2] F. Ritter, B. Standl, Promoting Student Competencies in Informatics Education by Combining Semantic Waves and Algorithmic Thinking, *Informatics in Education* 00 (2022). doi:10.15388/infedu.2023.07.
- [3] F. Ritter, B. Standl, Promoting Computational Thinking in Teacher Education - Combining Semantic Waves and Algorithmic Thinking, in: *Proceedings of the 2022 ACM Conference on International Computing Education Research - Volume 2, ICER '22*, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 2022, pp. 48–49. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3501709.3544285>. doi:10.1145/3501709.3544285.
- [4] A. Csizmadia, B. Standl, J. Waite, Integrating the constructionist learning theory with computational thinking classroom activities, *Informatics in Education* 18 (2019) 41–67.
- [5] B. Standl, Conceptual modeling and innovative implementation of person-centered computer science education at secondary school level, University of Vienna, Vienna, Austria (2013).